

E-security and management performance among small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria.

Eleberi Ebele Leticia
Department of Computer Science
Ebyfav2001@yahoo.com

Abstract

This paper investigates issues on E-security and management performance among small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Proxy of E-security was disaggregated into Web payment system, electronic fund transfer and mobile payment system and regressed on Small and medium enterprises performance from 2005-2019. Multiple regression ordinary least square method was employed to analysed data generated. This study found WPS, EFT and MPS has positive and direct effect on SMEP but only EFT revealed statistical significance at 5% critical level. The study also revealed all parameter estimate jointly impact on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises performance in Nigeria.

Keywords: *E-security, E-commerce, Web Payment System, Electronic Fund Transfer, Mobile Payment System*

1. Introduction

E- security is a data's piece security system and is particularly connected to the segment that influences e-business that incorporates PC security, information security and other more extensive domains of the data security. Today, privacy and security are a noteworthy sympathy toward electronic advances business offers security worries with other innovation in the field. Advancement in instalment framework empowers transaction to be carryout easily crosswise over outskirts and plastic cards are one of the essential methods for picking up to record regardless of where the client is living. In Africa, illustration, the connection of outskirts and the Euro' presentation have prompted a generous increment in cross outskirts transaction and related fraud.

E-commerce, that we all know of today has been existing for the past of ten years. Be that as it may, its antecedents, for example, material requirement planning (MRP), enterprise resource

planning. (ERP), electronic data interchange (EDI), have been existing for over forty years and as yet living. Electronic information interchanged is the electronic communication of business of business transaction, for example, confirmation and involves between organizations although interactive access may be part of it, electronic data interchange (EDI) implies computer to computer transaction into vendors database and ordering system. The details data of the Material requirement planning (MRP) and Enterprise resource planning (ERP) is covered.

1.1 Statement of the problem

E-security entails measures put forward to combat electronic commerce threat and other online or electronic malicious factors that negatively affect organizational performance online. Electronic or Information security is used to protect against unavoidable security forces ensure the continuity of business, and reduce destruction. Businesses recognize security as a critical issue even many lacks the knowledge

behind electronic security techniques, if the organization is not knowledgeable enough on the security protocols then it is not able to part on its employee's education about how its intellectual property can be guarded. Therefore for them to gain from their security management practices they must have the necessary insight into problems at hand and security management controls within the scope that they can effectively accommodate (PACIS, 2013). Fu-guo and Yujie (2010) opined that e-commerce security threats are not focused on as single aspect of electronic (e) commerce but spins around different aspects of e-commerce transactions. These transactions could include electronic payment processes, buying process, receiving process, registration and online storage. The authors argued that e-security issues are considered as both systems engineering and social issues which demands general participation of members of the society. The threats fighting against e-security has been classified differently by different authors like DiYanni (2012) classified them as malicious code attacks which include: viruses, worms, Trojan horses, logic bombs, denial of service attack i.e.-distributed denial of service, SYN Flooding and Phishing. Rahman and Lackey (2013) classified e-security threats as web server threats, database threats, reconnaissance, social engineering, port scanning, vulnerability scanning, e-commerce server attacks, physical attacks, malware, and denial of service which SMEs must put into consideration. Since E-security centres on data integrity, data confidentiality, data authenticity and data reliability, this study captures specifically variable with element of E-security that facilitate the performance of SMEs in Nigeria such as ; web payment system, mobile payment system and electronic fund transfers.

1.2 Objective of the study

The objective of this study is to investigate issues on E-security and management performance among small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The Specific objective of the study are to;

1. determine the effect of web payment system on the performance SMEs in Nigeria
2. evaluate the effect of electronic fund transfer on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria
3. Ascertain the effect of mobile payment system on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria

1.3 Research questions

This research paper is guided by the underlisted questions;

1. what effect has web payment E-security on performance of SMEs in Nigeria.
2. what is the of Electronic fund transfer E-security on performance of SMEs in Nigeria
3. to what extent has mobile payment system e-security affected the performance of SMEs in Nigeria

1.4 Research hypotheses

H₀: there is no significant relationship between web payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

H₀: there is no significant relationship between Electronic fund transfer and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

H₀: there is no significant relationship between mobile payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

1.5 Scope of the study

The content scope of this paper is to ascertain the effect e-security and management of the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. E-security

system was disaggregated into web payment system, electronic fund transfer and mobile payment system as published in CBN statistical bulletin various years regressed against SME performance in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of related literature

2.1 Conceptual E-security

Electronic security entails measures put forward to combat electronic commerce threats, Determines and other online or electronic malicious factors that negatively affect organizations Performance online. Electronic or Information security is used to protect against unavoidable Security forces, ensure the continuity of business, and reduce destruction. Businesses recognize Security as a critical issue even many lacks the knowledge behind electronic security techniques, if the organization is not knowledgeable enough on the security protocols then it is not able to impart on its employee's education about how its intellectual property can be guarded. Therefore, for firms to gain from their security management practices they must have the necessary insights into problems at hand and security management controls within the scope that they can effectively accommodate (PACIS, 2013). Fu-guo and Yujie (2010) opined that e-commerce security threats are not focused on as single aspect of electronic (e) commerce but spins around different aspects of e-commerce transactions. These transactions could include electronic payment processes, buying process, receiving process, registration and online storage. The authors argued that e-security issues are considered as both systems engineering and social issues which demands general participation of members of the society. The threats fighting against e-security has been classified differently by different authors like DiYanni (2012) classified them as malicious code attacks which include: viruses, worms, Trojan horses, logic bombs, denial of service attack i.e.-distributed denial of service, SYN Flooding and Phishing. Rahman and Lackey (2013) classified e-security

threats as web server threats, database threats, reconnaissance, social engineering. port scanning, vulnerability scanning, e-commerce server attacks, physical attacks, malware, and denial of service which SMEs must put into consideration.

2.1.1 Management Performance

Management performance is the measure of the extent an organization achieve its stated goals and objectives. Richard et al (2009) opined that performance in an organizational settings consist of three specific aspect of firm outcomes, that is financial performance, return on assets, return on investment are involve in that organizational performance. Secondly, product market

performance where sales, market share are involved and lastly shareholder return where total shareholder return, economic value added are involved. Kotane (2015) noted that management performance can be measured using both financial and non-financial dimensions. Managements performance measurement could be done via financial and non-financial performance indicators of the organizations such time, cost, quality, customer Satisfaction, stakeholders such as employees, investors, and suppliers are all critical measurement aspects (Kaplan, 1983). Performance can be measured using certain parameters like unit cost of production. Product specifications, delivery performance, product development, product innovation, and customer support and services Chairoel, Widyarto, &Pujani, 2015). Didier (2002) opined that performance consists in "achieving the goals that were given to you in convergence of enterprise orientations"

The author stated that performance is not a mere finding of an outcome, but rather a function of a comparison between the outcome and the set objectives. In other words, management performance is the measurement of what management previous set as target and what they eventually got as a result. Rolstadas (1998) considers that the performance of an

organizational system is a complex relationship consisting of seven performance criteria that must be adhered to and they include factors such as: effectiveness, efficiency, quality, productivity, and quality of work, innovation and profitability. The author noted that performance of organizations or individual form revolves around the criteria enlisted above.

2.1.2 Factors Influencing SMEs ICT Adoption in Nigeria

The use of information communication technology (ICT) has been widely embraced by various regions including developing and developed countries. Thus, various studies have delved into Similar studies and found different factors such Adebayo, Balogun and Kareem, (2013) indicated that cost, funds, infrastructure, skills and training, management support and government support attitude are the major elements or factors that influencing information communication technology (ICT) establishment adoption in Nigeria by SMEs. Further, Sajuyigbe and Alabi, (2012) also confirm that infrastructural, cost of acquisition, lack of finance, skills, management and government support are the main challenges of ICT adoption by SMES in Nigeria. Pinsonneault and Kraenmer (1993) outlined the factors into internal and external barriers that impede adoption of ICT by SMEs in developing countries. The internal barriers include; owner manager characteristics, cost and return on investment, and external barriers include; infrastructure, social, cultural, political, legal and regulatory. Factors such as owner/manager characteristics, the role of top management, firm characteristics, costs and return on investment, lack of adequate telecommunication infrastructures such as poor internet connectivity, lack of fixed telephone lines for end-users, dial-up access and the underdeveloped state of the Internet Service Providers (ISPs) have been identified by Kapurubandara and Lawson (2006) as problems that hinder SMEs' adoption of ICT in a developing country. While Chau (1995) proposed

that the owner's lack of knowledge of ICT technology and perceived benefits is a major barrier to the adoption of ICT. The lack of knowledge on how to use the technology and the low computer literacy are other contributing factors for not adopting ICT (Knol and Stroeken2001).

2.1.3 E-security Guidelines for SMEs in Nigeria

Despite the setbacks preventing SMEs from adopting and utilizing electronic business tractions, various elements could be considered to enhance e-security in order to achieve enhanced performance. The following are guides on how organizations can handle security issues as provided by Obodoeze et al (2012):

1. Provide end-to-end data encryption using strong cryptographic cipher engines (AES 128 bit) to enhance data confidentiality.
2. Create strong user authentication to improved confidentiality and integrity.
3. Establish Message Authentication Codes (MAC) to enhance data authentication and protection of data from unauthorized users.
4. Perform vulnerability and compliance system scan on all interconnected stakeholders on their network on a regular basis at a minimal fee to the stakeholders.

Further, Park, Robles, Hong, and Kim (2008) identified electronic security standards for SMEs which includes established standard and pragmatic approach. The established standards entails security frameworks developed by organizations to remain at a service quality and security while the pragmatic approach accommodates smaller companies than the standard security frameworks. In addition, Pipkin(2000) proposed a data security process model that consist of five facets: (1) inspection, (2) protection. (3) detection, (4) reaction, and (5)

reflection.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Davis' (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Davis Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) predicts information technology acceptance and usage. In this model the user's behavioral intention to use a technology is affected by their perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of the technology.

This model was originally developed for studying technology at work. Later it has been used as such or modified to study user acceptance of consumer services such as Internet services or e-commerce (Kaasinen, 2005). The Technology Acceptance Model constitutes a solid framework for identifying issues that may affect user acceptance of technical solutions. As Davis and Venkatesh (2004) have proved, the model can be enhanced from the original purpose of studying user acceptance of existing products to study planned product concepts, e.g. in the form of mock-ups. This indicates that Technology Acceptance Model could also be used in connection with technology development projects and processes to assess the usefulness of proposed solutions. Applied in this way, the model also supports the human-centered design approach.

Technology acceptance model (TAM) is currently the most effective tool for describing information systems adoption. It was developed by Davis (1989) to explain and predict computer-usage security behaviour. It has its theoretical root in Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Fishbein et al., 1975). TRA depicts that beliefs influence attitudes, which lead to intentions, and finally to behaviours. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) introduced two independent determinants, attitude towards behaviour and subjective norm.

Attitude toward behaviour refers to the degree that an individual has a positive or negative reaction towards a specific behaviour. Normative beliefs consider the probability that important persons or groups approve or disapprove of performing a specific behaviour.

According to the TRA, individuals' attitudes towards behaviours are determined by their most important beliefs and the consequences of performing specific behaviours. As Fishbein et al. (1975) demonstrated through their theory, behaviour is best predicted by intentions, and intentions are jointly determined by the person's attitude and subjective norm concerning the behaviour. TAM's proposition posits two constructs: Perceived usefulness (PU) which is defined as "the prospective user's subjective probability that using a specific application system will increase his or her job performance" and perceived ease of use (PEOU), which refers to the degree to which the prospective user expects the target system to be free of effort (Davis et al, 1989).

Both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have been used in examining users' acceptance of information systems. Perceived usefulness has been proven consistently as significant in attitude formation (Jiang et al., 2008; Klopping, 2004). TAM has also been employed to predict consumers' adoption of Web technology (Pavlou, 2003; Tan et al., 2014; Klopping). Lee et al. (2001) extended TAM with perceived risk (PR) and found that the TAM predicted individual purchasing behaviour online and that perceived risk affects perceived usefulness. Chen et al. (2002) also found TAM effective in evaluating online shopping at "virtual" on-line store. Building on these empirically validated views, the TAM is suitable for determining e-commerce but may not fully determine the users' intention to adopt the technology. Therefore, the study proposes an

extended TAM, with integration of task-technology fit model, trust, and perceived risk to better predict consumers' adoption of e-commerce. The original TAM was also modified by dropping perceived ease of use – perceived usefulness the path based on previous e-commerce adoption studies which argued that Web tools are exceptionally easy to use (Klopping et al., 2004). Also, to simplify TAM, the attitude construct was dropped and focused on the relationship between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on intention to use.

Trust is a belief that one can rely upon a promise made by another (Pavlou, 2003). Klopping and McKinney (2004) defines trust in electronic commerce as the subjective probability with which consumers believe that an online transaction with a web retailer will occur in a manner consistent with their expectations. Scholars have identified lack of trust as one of the main reasons for consumers' cynicism towards electronic commerce. In the context of e-commerce, trust beliefs include the online consumers' beliefs and expectancies about trust-related characteristics of the online seller (McKnight and Chervany, 2012). The online consumers desire the online sellers to be willing and able to act in the consumers' interests, to be honest in transactions (not divulging personal information to other vendors), and to be capable of delivering the ordered goods as agreed. According to Mahmood and Bagchi (2004), the trust factor has significant positive contributions to consumers' online shopping behaviour. Jiang et al (2008) argued that consumer trust is a critical enabler of successful online retailing and knowledge is one important factor influencing the level of trust. The work of Maskus (2013) and May (2017), among others presented integrated trust model with the technology acceptance model for business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okeke, Oboreh&Ezeaghaego (2016) examined the effects of e-commerce on the growth of small scale enterprises in Anambra State. The study adopted judgmental sampling technique. A sample size of 282 respondents was chosen through purposive sampling. The data used were generated from the selected small scale enterprises in Nnewi, Onitsha and Awka. The data generated were analyzed using percentage analysis while the hypotheses formulated were tested using Z-test statistics. The study found that business-to-customer (B2C) exerts significant effect on the performance of small scale enterprises. It also revealed that E-commerce adoption has significant effect on growth of small scale enterprises. It was recommended that small scale enterprises yet to adopt e-commerce technology should do so to remain competitive in their industries.

Oluwafemi, Christopher, Joel & Adeyinka (2016), researched on e-commerce in Nigeria: a survey of security awareness of customers and factors that influence acceptance. The study aimed at accessing the security awareness of customers of e-commerce sites in Nigeria, and identifying factors that influence acceptance of these platforms. Data were collected via the use of questionnaire and was analyzed using T-test. Results show that most customers are aware that their information are stored by the e-commerce sites, and are concerned about the security of their data on these sites and the possibility of their information to be transferred to third party without their knowledge or permission. Yet only few of them make effort to always check the security and privacy policies of the sites before making purchases. Also, only few users are conversant with security technologies for securing e-commerce platforms. The proposed

factors were found to be important or likely to influence transacting on e-commerce sites.

Akanbi & Akintunde (2018), studied E-commerce adoption and small medium scale Enterprises performance in Nigeria. The study aimed at examining the impact e-commerce adoption has on SMEs Operators performance. The study employed the use of a quantitative research approach. Based on the quantitative approach imbibed in the study, questionnaire was used to capture data that examined the objectives of the research. The questionnaire was distributed both manually and electronically to total sample of over 250 SMEs. Data collected were analysed using descriptive analysis. The study showed that e-commerce has potentials to improve the performance of SMEs operators and bring about expansion in business outlook if factors limiting the adoption of e-commerce like security issues, under developed infrastructures, poor delivery logistics and poor courier systems, infrastructure facilities, incompatibility of business with e-commerce etc., were eliminated. The study recommended improved infrastructural facilities and better strategies that will improve consumers and business technological knowledge and ensure favourable environment for ecommerce adoption.

Rita & John (2015) carried out a study on Determinant factors of e-commerce adoption by SMEs in developing country: evidence from Indonesia. The aim of this study is to investigate those factors that influence SMEs in developing countries in adopting ecommerce. A descriptive survey method using an on-line questionnaire was employed. Eleven variables were proposed as the factors that influence SMEs in adopting of e-commerce. These were organized into four groups, namely: technological factors, organizational factors, environmental factors and individual factors. A sample of 292 respondents was drawn from a population of 3,267 SMEs, a

response rate of 8.9%. To investigate the relationship between the variables, multiple regression analysis is used. The result shows that the individual factors play a significant role in adopting of e-commerce technology by SMEs in Indonesia. It was also found that perceived benefits, technology readiness, owners innovativeness, owners IT ability and owners IT experience are the determinant factors that influence Indonesian SMEs in their adopting e-commerce.

Kareem, Owomoyela, & Oyebamiji (2014), conducted a research on electronic commerce and business performance: an empirical investigation of business organizations in Nigeria. This research paper examined the impact of e-commerce on business performance with particular reference to the selected supermarkets in Ibadan metropolis. The study sample was made up of 8 Supermarkets. Structured questionnaire designed by the researchers were used to collect data from each operator and 5 staff respectively, totalling 48 respondents. Data analysis was conducted with simple regression analysis. The result showed that e-commerce adoption has significant impact on service operations, cost operation reductions and profit levels. It was concluded that adoption of e-commerce by Nigerian supermarkets will reduce transaction cost, improve service operations, expand business base, better understand the needs of foreign customers, and increase profit levels. The study recommended that the operators and staff of supermarkets should embark on more effective Information Technology (IT) training in order to further enhance their performance. It also recommends management of supermarkets should procure quality IT gadgets that will enhance efficiency and customers retention.

Kabuba (2014), carried out a study on e-commerce and performance of online businesses in Kenya. The aim of the study was to establish the performance of existing online businesses as well establish the relationship between e-commerce models and performance. The study targeted 30 online companies based in Nairobi County and a cross sectional survey design was adopted. Descriptive statistics was employed. The regression analysis model was then used for data analysis. The study findings revealed that some of the challenges affecting online businesses but to a moderate extent are: potential customers reluctance to shop online due to desire to touch/interact with the product prior to making a purchase, lack of personal contact with customers which might be beneficial to business, e-commerce software incompatibility with existing infrastructure, customer distrust regarding privacy of personal data and finally, customers general lack of trust for online businesses. It was recommended that the government needs to invest in the enactment of laws and regulatory infrastructure that supports online purchasing. Most importantly Kenyan consumers have to be more willingly to purchase products and services online.

Mutia, Ahmad, Aziz & Mohamad (2014), examined the relationship between e-commerce adoption and organization performance of hotel industry in Malaysia. This study uses a cross-sectional research design. Data was analysed using a statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 11. The study also found that there is a correlation between organization performance with E-commerce business network, and E-commerce competency. The research also employed stepwise regression analysis to look at dominant factor in predicting organizational performance. The research contributed to both academic research and management practice as it provide comprehensive impact of how e-

commerce adoption influence organizational performance at least in the case of Tourism industry in a small developing economy like Malaysia.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher adopt quasi experimental design to analyse data generated for E-security and management performance among small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. This choice of design will be employed since it involves the manipulation of independent variable without a random assignment of participants to conditions or order of conditions.

3.2 Sources of Data

This study employed secondary source as the sole source of data collection. The data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) online published bulletin reports various years. The data collected (and analyzed) enabled the realization of the research objectives, answering of the research questions and forming opinion of the assertions of the study's hypotheses. The quantitative data collected covered the various proxies for the dependent and independent variables of the study namely SMEs performance (SMEP), Web payment System (WPS), Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) and mobile payment system (MPS), for the period of 13 years covering 2005 – 2017.

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Analysis was employed in the analysis of data with the aid of E-view statistical package Version 9.0. The choice of this technique for this study is based on the uniqueness and time frame of the data collected and it give room for expressing the relationship in a mathematical form. That is, it

provides an estimated equation which expresses the functional relationship between the dependent and independent; such that one variable can be predicted given the value of the other variable. Individual significance test using t-statistics (prob) was utilized in the hypothesis test. The researcher thus adjudged this technique as being suitable for the analysis of this study. However, the t-statistics was adopted in testing each of the hypotheses of this study.

3.3.1 Model Specification

To capture the proxies for the variables in the three specific objectives of the study, the models bellow was developed:

$$SMEP = F(WPS, MPS, EFT) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The above equation can be rewritten into multiple regression models as follows:

$$SMEP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WPS + \beta_2 EFT + \beta_3 MPS + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: SMEP = Small and Medium Enterprises Performance.

EFT = Electronic Fund Transfer

WPS = Web Payment System

MPS = Mobile

MPS= Mobile payment system

Where: β_0 is the intercept of the multiple regression line

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \& \beta_3$ are the coefficient of the explanatory

YEAR	LOGsmep	LOGwps	LOGeft	LOGmps
2005	0.40567	1.659441	3.894241	0.09691
2006	-0.00636	1.658584	4.01508	0.276462
2007	-0.06926	1.892762	3.992902	0.404834
2008	-0.76133	1.940765	4.018405	0.346353
2009	-0.77138	1.925054	4.078755	0.103804
2010	-0.86505	1.398808	4.055259	0.822822
2011	-0.78947	1.775319	4.080594	1.278296
2012	-0.87687	1.499238	4.135452	1.498439
2013	-0.87615	1.675011	4.155558	2.15472
2014	-0.91391	1.869488	4.164846	2.539662
2015	-1.02028	1.961807	4.116843	2.64577
2016	-0.49485	2.121758	4.163901	2.879037
2017	-0.58503	2.266224	4.174538	3.042181
2018	-0.5376	2.607027	4.042613	3.262617
2019	-0.38722	2.679546	4.113586	3.640635

(independent) variables

ϵ is the stochastic variable or error term

4.0 Data Presentation, Analysis And Interpretations

4.1 Data Presentation

Data collected for this study include data on aggregate Small and Medium Enterprises Performance (SMEP), Web Payment System (WPS), Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) and Mobile Payment System (MPS). The data are presented on table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Data on, SMEP, WPS, EFT, MPS for the period covering 2005 – 2019.

YEAR	SMEP	WPS	EFT	MPS
2005	2.54	45.65	7838.64	1.25
2006	0.99	45.56	10353.33	1.89
2007	0.85	78.12	9837.89	2.54
2008	0.17	87.25	10432.91	2.22
2009	0.17	84.15	11988.23	1.27
2010	0.14	25.05	11356.89	6.65
2011	0.16	59.61	12039.09	18.98
2012	0.13	31.57	13,660.03	31.51

2013	0.13	47.32	14,307.32	142.80
2014	0.12	74.04	14,616.58	346.47
2015	0.10	91.58	13,087.09	442.35
2016	0.32	132.36	14,584.80	756.90
2017	0.26	184.60	14,946.46	1,102.00
2018	0.29	404.60	11,030.96	1,830.70
2019	0.41	478.13	12,989.32	4,371.55

Source: CBN statistical bulletin various edition.

Table 4.1: Data on, SMEP, WPS, EFT, MPS for the period covering 2005 – 2019.

Ms Excel computation from table 4.1 above

The above data are in different bases; therefore, to bring the data in the same base, we calculate the logarithm for the data on each of the variables.

4.2 Data Analysis

Data analysis in this section is of two parts; the pre-test (diagnostic test) and model estimation as presented in the previous section. The paper employs the use of ordinary least square method of data analysis as the suitable tool in determining the effect E-security on SMEs performance in Nigeria.

4.2.1 Test for stationarity (Unit root test)

Having subjected PAT, ROA, ATM, POS, MPS to stationarity test Using Augmented Dickey-

Fuller test statistics, the following results were obtained.

Table 4.2.1: Augmented Dickey Fuller Stationarity Test Result

Variables	Critical value@ 5%	P-value
SMEP	-2.098896	0
WPS	-2.098896	0
ETF	-3.098896	0
MPS	-3.098896	0

Source: Extracts from Appendix 1

Table 4.2.1 shows that the time series data collected for the four (4) variables are all stationary at level. With this, we conclude that the time series data used in the analysis of this paper are all stationary and are therefore adjudged valid for the analysis using OLS estimate since all variables are stationary at level; findings of the analysis are thus reliable for policy decisions.

4.2.2 Result of Heteroskedasticity Test

F-statistic	0.526247	Prob. F(3,11)	0
Obs*R-squared	1.882631	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0
Scaled explained SS	0.344145	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0

Source: E-view result output 2021.

The test above reveals the presence of homoscedasticity since the observed R-square

probability value of 0.5971 is greater the critical value of 0.05. Indicating that the variance of the parameters is consistent overtime.

Log likelihood	-0.845958	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.644116
F-statistic	4.844393	Durbin-Watson stat	1.733670
Prob(F-statistic)	0.021892		

Source: E-view version 9.0 statistical Result, 2021

4.2.3 Normality Test

The above result reveals p-value of jargua-bera statistic as 0.578682 indicating that the variables are normally distributed since the probability value is greater than 5%.

Table 4.2.4 Ordinary least square estimated result

Dependent Variable: LOGSMEP
Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:03
Sample: 2005 2019
Included observations: 15

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	17.28076	6.895058	2.506253	0.0292
LOGWPS	0.133132	0.352754	0.377408	0.7131
LOGEFT	4.461725	1.642601	2.716256	0.0201
LOGMPS	0.058296	0.136994	0.425538	0.6787

R-squared	0.569188	Mean dependent var	0.569939
Adjusted R-squared	0.451694	S.D. dependent var	0.403732
S.E. of regression	0.298955	Akaike info criterion	0.646128
Sum squared resid	0.983112	Schwarz criterion	0.834941

The result on the above table reveals that the coefficient of LOGWPS is positive with the value of 0.133132; the coefficient of LOGEFT is positive at 4.461725 while the coefficient of LOGMPS is positive with the value of 0.058296. it was evident from the result that all the parameter estimates are positive related to the performance of small and medium enterprises. The value of the intercept (C) is 17.28076, indicating that the collective effect of the independent variables on ROA is positive.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

To ascertain the significance of these results, the t-statistics results of each of the independent variables were considered as follows;

Test of Hypothesis 1

H₀: there is no significant relationship between web payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

In testing this first hypothesis of the study, the regression result on table 4.3 reveal the p-value (t-stat probability) of the first independent variable web payment system (WPS) as 0.7131; which is greater than the significant level of 0.05 (5%) i.e. $P > 0.05$. This result indicates an insignificant effect exists WPS and SMEP. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between web payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria and consequently reject the associating alternative hypothesis that a significant relationship exists between web payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis 2

H₀: there is no significant relationship between Electronic fund transfer and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

From the result of regression analysis on table 4.3, the p-value (t-stat probability) of electronic fund transfer was obtained as (EFT) 0.0201; which is less than the significant level of 0.05 (5%) i.e. $P < 0.05$. This result indicates that a significant effect exists. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis which states that 0.0201 and consequently accept the alternative hypothesis that a significant relationship exist between ETF and SMEP.

Test of Hypothesis 3

H₀: there is no significant relationship between mobile payment system and performance of SMEs in Nigeria

In testing the third hypothesis of the study, we adopt the test of significance result from the regression analysis on table 4.3. From the result, the p-value (t-stat probability) of the third independent variable mobile payment system is 0.6787; which is greater than significant level of 0.05 (5%) i.e. $P > 0.05$. This result shows an insignificant effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis which states that mobile payment system has no significant effect on performance of SMEP and consequently reject the alternative hypothesis that state otherwise.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The findings from the analysis and test statistics are discussed in line with the empirical review this study. Discussion of the findings is as follows:

1. In respect of the first objective and the first hypothesis of this study, we find that web payment system has insignificant positive effect on small and medium enterprises performance in Nigeria. This implies that e-security as proxy by web payment being an electronic instrument of e-commerce has no significant effect on SMEP in Nigeria. This result is not in agreement with Kareem, Owomoyela, & Oyebamiji (2014) with who hold that e-security significantly affect the SMEP.
2. The second findings of this study reveal electronic fund transfer to be statistically significant with SMEP. This disagrees with Oluwafemi, Christopher, Joel & Adeyinka (2016) who researched on e-commerce in Nigeria but support the findings of Kareem, Owomoyela, & Oyebamiji (2014).
3. The study also revealed mobile payment system has positive but insignificantly related to small and medium enterprises in Nigeria. This finding disagrees with the work of Kareem, Owomoyela, & Oyebamiji (2014) who are of the opinion that e-security adoption has significant impact on service operations, cost operation reductions and profit levels. They concluded that adoption of e-security by SMEs will reduce transaction cost, improve service operations, expand business base, better understand the needs of foreign customers, and increase profit levels.

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Appendix

Data set for Small and Medium enterprises, Web Payment System Electronic Fund Transfer and Mobile Payment System

YEAR	LOGsmep	LOGwps	LOGeft	LOGmps
2005	0.40567	1.659441	3.894241	0.09691
2006	-0.00636	1.658584	4.01508	0.276462
2007	-0.06926	1.892762	3.992902	0.404834
2008	-0.76133	1.940765	4.018405	0.346353
2009	-0.77138	1.925054	4.078755	0.103804
2010	-0.86505	1.398808	4.055259	0.822822
2011	-0.78947	1.775319	4.080594	1.278296
2012	-0.87687	1.499238	4.135452	1.498439
2013	-0.87615	1.675011	4.155558	2.15472
2014	-0.91391	1.869488	4.164846	2.539662
2015	-1.02028	1.961807	4.116843	2.64577
2016	-0.49485	2.121758	4.163901	2.879037
2017	-0.58503	2.266224	4.174538	3.042181
2018	-0.5376	2.607027	4.042613	3.262617
2019	-0.38722	2.679546	4.113586	3.640635

Source: CBN Statistical bulletin various years

UNIT ROOT TEST

Null Hypothesis: LOGEFT has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.999900	0.0193
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.004425	
5% level	-2.098896	
10% level	-2.690439	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.
Warning: Probabilities and critical values calculated for 20 observations
and may not be accurate for a sample size of 14

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LOGEFT)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:05
Sample (adjusted): 2006 2019
Included observations: 14 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGEFT(-1)	-0.489452	0.163156	-2.999900	0.0111
C	2.011546	0.665437	3.022895	0.0106
R-squared	0.428555	Mean dependent var		0.015668
Adjusted R-squared	0.380935	S.D. dependent var		0.060585
S.E. of regression	0.047669	Akaike info criterion		-3.117522
Sum squared resid	0.027268	Schwarz criterion		-3.026228
Log likelihood	23.82265	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.125972
F-statistic	8.999403	Durbin-Watson stat		2.305977
Prob(F-statistic)	0.011069			

Null Hypothesis: LOGMPS has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.300899	0.0289
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.004425	
5% level	-3.098896	
10% level	-2.690439	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.
Warning: Probabilities and critical values calculated for 20 observations
and may not be accurate for a sample size of 14

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LOGMPS)
Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:06

Sample (adjusted): 2006 2019

Included observations: 14 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGMPS(-1)	0.018468	0.061375	0.300899	0.7686
C	0.224958	0.117391	1.916304	0.0794
R-squared	0.007489	Mean dependent var		0.253123
Adjusted R-squared	-0.075221	S.D. dependent var		0.255635
S.E. of regression	0.265075	Akaike info criterion		0.313956
Sum squared resid	0.843177	Schwarz criterion		0.405250
Log likelihood	-0.197689	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.305505
F-statistic	0.090540	Durbin-Watson stat		1.824139
Prob(F-statistic)	0.768641			

Null Hypothesis: LOGSMEP has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.059408	0.0335
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.004425	
5% level	-2.098896	
10% level	-2.690439	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Warning: Probabilities and critical values calculated for 20 observations
and may not be accurate for a sample size of 14

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LOGSMEP)

Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:07
Sample (adjusted): 2006 2019
Included observations: 14 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGSMEP(-1)	-0.430912	0.140848	-3.059408	0.0099
C	-0.307852	0.099627	-3.090055	0.0094
R-squared	0.438202	Mean dependent var		-0.056635
Adjusted R-squared	0.391385	S.D. dependent var		0.270587
S.E. of regression	0.211095	Akaike info criterion		-0.141455
Sum squared resid	0.534732	Schwarz criterion		-0.050161
Log likelihood	2.990185	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.149906
F-statistic	9.359975	Durbin-Watson stat		2.206350
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009910			

Null Hypothesis: LOGWPS has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=3)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.356727	0.0042
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.004425	
5% level	-3.098896	
10% level	-2.690439	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.
Warning: Probabilities and critical values calculated for 20 observations
and may not be accurate for a sample size of 14

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
Dependent Variable: D(LOGWPS)
Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:08

Sample (adjusted): 2006 2019
Included observations: 14 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGWPS(-1)	-0.077121	0.216190	-0.356727	0.0275
C	0.217473	0.410596	0.529653	0.0060
R-squared	0.010493	Mean dependent var		0.072865
Adjusted R-squared	-0.071966	S.D. dependent var		0.235842
S.E. of regression	0.244181	Akaike info criterion		0.149749
Sum squared resid	0.715492	Schwarz criterion		0.241043
Log likelihood	0.951759	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.141298
F-statistic	0.127254	Durbin-Watson stat		2.491090
Prob(F-statistic)	0.727490			

ORDINARY LEAST SQUARE ESTIMATE

Dependent Variable: LOGSMEP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:03

Sample: 2005 2019

Included observations: 15

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	17.28076	6.895058	2.506253	0.0292
LOGWPS	0.133132	0.352754	0.377408	0.7131
LOGEFT	4.461725	1.642601	2.716256	0.0201
LOGMPS	0.058296	0.136994	0.425538	0.6787
R-squared	0.569188	Mean dependent var		-0.569939
Adjusted R-squared	0.451694	S.D. dependent var		0.403732
S.E. of regression	0.298955	Akaike info criterion		0.646128
Sum squared resid	0.983112	Schwarz criterion		0.834941
Log likelihood	-0.845958	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.644116
F-statistic	4.844393	Durbin-Watson stat		1.733670
Prob(F-statistic)	0.021892			

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	LOGSMEP	LOGEFT	LOGMPS	LOGWPS
Mean	-0.569939	4.080172	1.666169	1.928722
Median	-0.761335	4.080594	1.498439	1.892762
Maximum	0.405670	4.174538	3.640635	2.679546
Minimum	-1.020281	3.894241	0.096910	1.398808
Std. Dev.	0.403732	0.078630	1.277007	0.366422
Skewness	1.121863	-0.753402	0.090471	0.741745
Kurtosis	3.331273	3.028225	1.463375	2.852947
Jarque-Bera	3.215033	1.419535	1.496223	1.388978
Probability	0.200385	0.491758	0.473259	0.499330
Sum	-8.549083	61.20257	24.99254	28.93083
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.281997	0.086557	22.83045	1.879714
Observations	15	15	15	15

Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.526247	Prob. F(3,11)	0.6733
Obs*R-squared	1.882631	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.5971
Scaled explained SS	0.344145	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.9515

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID^2

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:25

Sample: 2005 2019

Included observations: 15

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.203957	1.361047	0.884581	0.3953
LOGWPS	0.015471	0.069632	0.222187	0.8282
LOGEFT	-0.288087	0.324241	-0.888499	0.3933
LOGMPS	0.004315	0.027042	0.159580	0.8761
R-squared	0.125509	Mean dependent var		0.065541
Adjusted R-squared	-0.112989	S.D. dependent var		0.055936
S.E. of regression	0.059012	Akaike info criterion		-2.598973
Sum squared resid	0.038307	Schwarz criterion		-2.410160
Log likelihood	23.49230	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.600984
F-statistic	0.526247	Durbin-Watson stat		2.211243
Prob(F-statistic)	0.673270			

NORMALITY TEST

Series: Residuals	
Sample 2005 2019	
Observations 15	
Mean	9.73e-15
Median	0.006671
Maximum	0.390139
Minimum	-0.391643
Std. Dev.	0.264995
Skewness	-0.043500
Kurtosis	1.679835
Jarque-Bera	1.094003
Probability	0.578682

MULTICOLLINEARITY TEST

Variance Inflation Factors
Date: 05/08/21 Time: 17:26
Sample: 2005 2019
Included observations: 15

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
C	47.54183	7979.155	NA
LOGWPS	0.124435	80.30682	2.617125
LOGLEFT	2.698139	7541.414	2.613114
LOGMPS	0.018767	13.53833	4.794096